

Kinetics of Oxidation of Dimethyl-Sulphoxide by Ce (IV) in Aqueous Perchloric Acid

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The kinetics of oxidation of dimethyl sulphoxide by Ce(IV) was investigated in aqueous perchloric acid media at 25-40°. The reaction rate is first order with respect to [Ce(IV)] and [DMSO]. The reaction rate is retarded by [NaHSO₄] and accelerated by [HClO₄]. The thermodynamic parameters have been computed.

OXIDATION of organic and inorganic substrates by Ce(IV) has been extensively studied¹⁻¹⁸. The kinetics of oxidation of organic sulphur compounds, of late, received considerable attention owing to their biological importance. The kinetic studies involving organic sulphur compounds have been reported with a variety of metal ion oxidants such as V(V)²⁰, Ce(IV)²¹⁻²³, Co(III)²³ and Mn(III)²⁴. The oxidation of dimethyl sulphoxide to sulphone has been reported with Cr(VI)²⁵ and permanganate²⁶. Recently Cox and Gibson²⁷ reported the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of dimethyl sulphoxide with bromine in aqueous solution. The kinetics of oxidation of dimethyl sulphoxide to sulphone with one electron oxidants do not seem to have received much attention. In the present study, the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of dimethyl sulphoxide by Ce(IV) in aqueous perchloric acid have been reported.

Experimental

Ceric ammonium nitrate used was of E. Merck, G. R. quality. Dimethyl sulphoxide was purified by distillation under reduced pressure from calcium hydride. Inorganic materials were of Analar grade. A stock solution of Ce(IV) in perchloric acid was prepared as follows: Ceric ammonium hydroxide was precipitated from a solution of ceric ammonium nitrate by ammonium hydroxide. The precipitate was allowed to settle (48 hr), leached several times with water, dissolved in perchloric acid (Analar, Riedel) and filtered. A dilute solution of Ce(IV) in 4M perchloric acid was obtained and standardised against ferrous ammonium sulphate using N-phenyl anthranilic acid as indicator.

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

Stoichiometric experiments were carried out in the usual way with excess Ce(IV) until there was no change in the concentration of Ce(IV) which was estimated against Fe(II) solution. The reaction occurs according to the following scheme

The product of dimethyl sulphoxide was characterised to be dimethyl sulphone. The product was identified

by taking the glc of the reaction mixture and comparing the retention time with authentic dimethyl sulphone. Further, the formation of dimethyl sulphone was confirmed by isolating the compound²⁵ and taking the IR spectrum. The IR spectrum of the compound (KBr disc) shows a strong band at 1072 cm⁻¹ due to sulphoxide groupings.

The reaction was initiated by mixing appropriate volume of the reactants kept at the desired temperature. Known volumes of the reaction mixture were withdrawn and quenched in excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate and the residual Fe(II) was titrated by Ce(IV) solution using ferroin as the indicator. The rate constants were computed from duplicate experiments. Constant ionic strength was maintained by adding sodium perchlorate.

Results and Discussion

At constant concentrations of DMSO (0.18M) and perchloric acid (1M), ionic strength (1.5M) and temperature (35°) and by varying the Ce(IV) concentration, a first-order dependence with respect to Ce(IV) was observed. The reaction order with respect to DMSO was also unity. At constant μ , the rate of oxidation increases with [H⁺] and a plot of 1/k_{obs} versus 1/[DMSO] was linear making an intercept on the 1/k_{obs} axis. The fact that the data could be treated according to Lineweaver and Burk²⁸ shows complexation between the reactants. (The spectrophotometric analysis was also made for complex formation by using a Beckman UV spectrophotometer at 25°. For ceric perchlorate, the absorption maxima were at 240 and 251 nm, whereas for the reaction mixture an additional absorption maxima was observed around 305 nm indicating the presence of a new species, probably the complex). Such complexation has also been postulated by Mahadevan²⁹ in Mn(III) oxidation of DMSO.

The effect of [bisulphate] on the rate of reaction was investigated. The bisulphate ions retard the reaction rate considerably, probably because sulphate complexes are less reactive.

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Cerium(IV) is present as an anionic species in sulphuric, nitric and hydrochloric acids and as cationic species in perchloric acid. Depending upon the concentration of perchloric acid, ceric ion may be present in this medium³⁰ as $[\text{Ce}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_9]^{4+}$ and $[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_7]^{3+}$ besides $[\text{Ce}-\text{O}-\text{Ce}]^{6+}$ and $[\text{Ce}_3\text{O}_3]^{6+}$. Since the predominant species is monomeric in the perchloric acid concentration range³¹ 0.2-2.0 M, the equilibrium can be written as follows³⁰ :

In the perchloric acid medium studied in the present experimental condition, II is the active species. The species II can react with dimethyl sulphoxide to form the complex(III) by the rapid substitution of water molecule. The electron transfer in complex(III) results in the liberation of free radical, which in subsequent stages is converted to the sulphone by reacting with water molecule. The reaction scheme is represented below :

From the above equations, the expression was derived to be :

$$5. \quad \frac{-d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Ce(IV)}]_T$$

$$= \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{Ce(IV)}] [\text{DMSO}] [\text{H}^+]}{K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+] [\text{DMSO}] + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + 1}$$

Which rearranges to equation (7), where k_{obs} is the observed rate constant.

$$6. \quad 1/k_{\text{obs}} = 1/k_3 + \frac{1}{[\text{DMSO}]} \frac{K_1 [\text{H}^+] + 1}{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{H}^+]}$$

Accordingly, at constant $[\text{H}^+]$, a plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{DMSO}]$ should be linear and it is observed to be so. From the above plot the values of k_3 were computed to be 1×10^{-3} , 1.43×10^{-3} and $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at 25°, 30° and 35° respectively. Values of K_1 at 10 and 25° are reported³² to be 1.5 and 5.2 respectively and graphically the values of K_1 were computed to be 8.12 and 12.10 at 30° and 35° respectively. Hence, from the rate expression, the values of K_2 at the above temperatures were computed to be 19.05, 16.77 and 11.48 respectively.

The value of ΔE_s for the decomposition of the complex was computed by plotting $\log k_3$ versus $1/T$ at three different temperatures was found to be 19.1 K. cal/mole and the corresponding entropy and enthalpy

of activation for the steps were evaluated to be 20.60 cal mole⁻¹K⁻¹ and 18.40 K. cal/mole respectively.

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF FIRST ORDER RATE ON [DMSO]

[DMSO] $k \times 10^4(\text{sec}^{-1})$	0.16	0.18	0.2	0.22	0.24
	3.68	4.16	4.64	5.12	5.60

TABLE 2—KINETIC DATA FOR THE OXIDATION OF DMSO BY CE(IV) IN AQUEOUS PERCHLORIC ACID.

[HC10 ₄] M	[DMSO] M	Temp. °C	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4(\text{sec}^{-1})$
0.5	0.14	25	0.77
		30	1.02
		35	1.35
		40	1.76
0.8	0.16	25	1.59
		30	2.37
		35	3.52
		40	4.80
1	0.18	25	1.90
		30	3.20
		35	4.16
		40	7.60
1.2	0.2	25	2.20
		30	3.80
		35	6.76
		40	11.23

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF [BISULPHATE] ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF DMSO BY CE (IV).

[NaHSO ₄] $k \times 10^4(\text{sec}^{-1})$	0.021	0.032	0.042	0.051
	1.28	1.01	0.95	0.80

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